

D5.1 Segmentation of DIHs services and business models per thematic/ topic/activities

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Executive Summary

The objective of the work package (WP) 5 “Exploring business models” is to identify, develop and promote the diversity of new business models that can foster knowledge sharing and technologies transfer between European DIHs while enabling the sustainable development of new business opportunities for them all.

By helping DIHs setting-up the framework of a Pan-European collaboration between them, DIHNET.EU aims at reinforcing the **smart specialisation** and at generating **cross fertilization** between technology oriented and sectorial DIHs.

To achieve this aim, the first task the WP5 had two main objectives:

- to create an overview of the existing sustainable business models for DIHs pan-EU collaboration networks;
- to collect inputs from existing organisation working as DIH in order to identify the potential business models to be developed when this Pan-European collaboration did not exist yet.

In order to map DIHs networks services and business models with a relevant segmentation, a survey elaborated by BLUMORPHO in strong cooperation with TNO and the WP1 & 3 has been sent to all the DIHs registered on the DIHNET community and to project coordinators of DIHs networks.

In the same time, work was done on the data already available in the catalogue to identify the services that were already made available by the DIHs and the services that were less prevalent.

In addition to this analysis, a conceptual analysis of the complex ecosystem in which DIHs operate has been included. This analysis is based on the experience and observations of the DIHNET partners. The conceptual analysis outlines the challenges of establishing collaboration and also in defining the possible services with added value for EU collaboration and the funding difficulties to make these services sustainable.

From those paralleled works, a few trends have been identified or confirmed and explained more in details in the deliverable.

- A majority of DIHs rely mainly on public funding;
- A majority of them think this is a structural and natural consequence as they address some market failures and need some strong public commitment to compensate those failures;
- A few of them express their interest to increase the proportion of funding coming from the private sector but stressed the need for time to do so.
- A small but “active” minority of them are also receiving private funding. They are considered as active as it is a real profession of faith for them to answer to the need of the Industry and to have the companies paying for the services they provide to them.
- Collaboration on pan-EU level can be seen as beneficial but a distinction should be made among the different services. Some services such as access to expertise can add value to the DIH clients but there are still challenges to establish a structural collaboration. For the DIHs themselves and indirectly their clients, there are also benefits to offer some services (such as strategic agenda setting) on a higher level services. Yet, financing such activities is not straightforward and requires finding various suitable business models.

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1 Introduction

The main objective of the work package 5 (WP5) “Exploring business models” is to identify, develop and promote the diversity of new business models that foster knowledge sharing and technologies transfer between European DIHs while enabling the sustainable development of new business opportunities for them all.

As stated in the grant agreement, the overall aim of this WP is “*to identify and define relevant business model for a sustainable network in:*

- *Leveraging on the high added value of the strong complementarity that can be generated in engaging DIHs networks collaboration whether they focus on specific topics and regions while working in close collaboration with DIHs CSA.*
- *Attract investment for the sustainability of this network of networks in addressing both the public funding agencies objectives but also in generating a critical mass addressing expectations from the private fields to invest in the transformation of the European industry through digitisation.*
- *Align business models with the services offered by DIHs and to be provided in the future to address the need of European SMEs but also to reinforce the value of collaboration between DIHs.*
- *Engage a Memorandum of Understanding between innovation stakeholders including DIHs and their network, public and private investors for collaboration.*
- *Set up an agile governance to ensure the growth of the network and to operate its sustainability.”*

By helping European DIHs to set-up the framework of a Pan-European collaborations between them, DIHNET.EU aims at reinforcing the **smart specialisation** and at generating **cross fertilization** between technology oriented and sectorial DIHs.

To achieve this aim, the first task of the WP5 had been to look at the current situation and the business models currently employed by different DIHs and to explore if different typologies could be distinguished. For this, the task was planned around analysis of the DIHs operating models, looking for possible segmentation considering criteria like DIH thematic and sectorial activities, local, regional or European activities and a first assessment of their maturity and impact on SMEs. The goal of the segmentation is to get a good understanding of the “DIHs European ecosystem”. Such knowledge is expected to help building the European added-value through win-win collaborations.

The implementation of the task 5.1 involved:

- To set-up a conceptual framework discussing the different levels/entities active in Europe and how these differences relate to the business models
- to create an overview of the existing sustainable business models for DIHs networks’ Pan-European collaboration; to collect inputs from existing organisations working as DIH in order to identify the potential business models to be developed when this Pan-European collaboration does not exist yet.

In order to map DIHs networks services and business models with a relevant segmentation, a survey elaborated by BLUMORPHO in strong cooperation with TNO and the WP1 & 3 has been sent to all the

DIHs registered on the DIHNET community and to project coordinators of DIHs networks. Following the dissemination of the survey, a first digital workshop has been organised on 22nd July to share the results and start the discussion between DIHs. The idea of this online workshop was to create synergies with the WP1 and to make the best of the working groups developed on the DIHNET community to start exchanging best practices on business models. The online workshop on the survey has been designed also as a follow-up of the breakout sessions organised on 1st July during the DIHs working groups meeting of the European Commission. The requirement to build sustainable business models for Pan-European collaboration had been discussed during this meeting in small working groups and first inputs had been shared during the plenary session.

In the same time, in order to valorise the catalogue of DIHs and to not miss the quantitative approach of DIHs activities that it allows, a data analysis of the information already available in the catalogue had been performed. The objective of this analysis was to proceed to a kind of market analysis of the services provided by DIHs, to identify the services that were already made available by most of the DIHs and those that were the most difficult to find and try to find possibilities for collaboration.

From the information gathered through the qualitative and quantitative approach, a huge diversity of segmentation criteria can be foreseen that will be developed later on in this deliverable.

- **creation date:** the first DIHs were Innovation Actions (IA) with technology focus built around competence centres versus local DIHs that are now developing in order to implement the Digitising European Industry Strategy (DEI strategy) designed by the European Commission. The vague and evolving concept of DIHs has brought a great diversity in the DIHs landscape.
- **initiating authority & starting point:** the European Commission and the projects funded under H2020 for the technical DIHs (IAs) versus the Regional/local public authorities for the new generation of DIHs that are dedicated to the development of a territory.
- **Ecosystem:** looking at whether the initiative is an individual DIH or a network or another initiative such as an IA, which would have a completely different ecosystem.
- **geographical reach:** the majority of current DIHs are focusing on a regional and national reach. A few of them - and mainly DIHs networks or IAs - can proud themselves or are willing to have a European reach.
- **services provided and objectives:** it seems that individual DIH and local DIH are more specialised regarding their technical expertise and that they provide less services than networks. Some DIH clearly have global ambitions to cover all the set of digital services related to digital transformation when others clearly plan to focus on very specific technologies.
- **funding scheme:** those having some private funding in their financial scheme being a smaller portion of all DIHs
- **business models** employed
- **team/consortium/partners' association:** looking at the different organizations that can support the DIH and possible barriers.

2 Segmentation of DIHs in Europe: a quantitative approach based on the DIHs catalogue

The DIHs catalogue developed by the JRC provides already a lot of information to be integrated in DIHNET mapping action. Therefore, the segmentation analysis will focus on this already rich data set.

The DIHs mapped in the catalogue includes the following criteria.

- **38 Countries:** EU members + geographical Europe
- **3 Evolutionary stages:** in preparation, fully operational, no more in exploitation
- **15 services** identified as important to be provided
- **26 Technical competences**
- **The 8 TRLs** the DIHs focus on
- **29 different market sectors**
- **Funding sources**

The DIH catalogue offers a good starting point to analyse the typologies of DIHs in Europe. Currently there are more than 400 DIHs registered in the catalogue, nearly 300¹ of which are fully functional. The analysis of this database will allow us later on to see the progress from the initial formation of the Catalogue till now and also to further try and segment the DIHs.

Previous analysis of the catalogue² made in 2017 suggested that:

- Digital Innovation Hubs were new type of entity, with many of the hubs starting operation around 2014-2015 utilizing a mix of funding sources;
- In 2017, DIHs were also found to have already a broad services portfolio and to aim at different segments of customers with SMEs often being the main target group.

In July 2019, 290 Digital Innovation Hubs were registered as fully active within the DIHs catalogue of the European Commission. It was decided to make an analysis of the information provided within the catalogue on this 290 DIHs to have an exhaustive and quantitative approach of a possible segmentation of DIHs in the current European Innovation landscape. It was decided to only review the fully operational entities as those under development might still need to develop some of the characteristics studied (eg. they might not yet have 3 showcases of services provided, which might also have impact on other characteristics – such as focus on sector, etc).

¹ The data analysed for this deliverable were issued from the 290 operational DIHs included in the JRC catalogue in July 2019.

² Arjen Goetheer, Maurits Butter (2017), Final report Digital Innovation Hubs Catalogue SMART 2016/0002, TNO 2017 R11340, available at: publications.tno.nl/publication/34626116/UNdvT9/TNO-2017-R11340.pdf

2.1 Statistical data analysis of the DIHs catalogue

We have decided to work on a selection of the various criteria proposed in the catalogue, focusing on those which were deemed the more contributing to the DIHs operational and business models:

- 9 organizational forms;
- 10 funding sources;
- 28 market sectors;
- 15 services provided;
- 25 digital technologies focus;
- 5 customers' types.

Using an Ascending Hierarchical Classification (AHC), combining all those criteria and their related variables, we were able to identify some trends that are indeed structuring the European DIHs landscape and can constitute a first segmentation of this DIHs landscape. The community of those 290 DIHs can be segmented into 3 homogeneous groups that will be detailed further in this analysis:

- those with the large range of technologies available and focusing more on business and ecosystem services;
- those in the average;
- those that are more technically focused.

2.1.1 organisational form

The organisational form taken by the DIHs is important to have in mind as their status will have an impact on the rules applicable to their activities. This will have an impact on their funding, on how the DIHs will be able to establish contract with services providers, will be able to hire external skills and set-up partnerships, be they local or international, etc...

Organisational Form	DIHs population (total 100%)
(part of) Public organization (part of RTO, or university)	99
Networked organization, without formal structure	54
(Part of) Private organisation	45
Public Private Partnership	35
Foundation	27
Joint venture	13
Project (formalized end time)	10
Other	4
Governmental agency	2

The results clearly indicate that about a third of the studied 290 hubs are (part of) public organizations. In the following tables analysing the other segmentation criteria, a DIH can enter into several categories so the global amount is not 100%.

2.1.2 Funding sources

Here it is important to notice what have been confirmed also through the questionnaire that has been shared by DIHNET to its community in July 2019: the prevalence of regional and national funding in the development of DIHs. This highlights the importance of such continuous (usually longer-term) and stable funding for the fundincion of the DIHs. Memberships, while not insignificant, appear to be mentioned by only about a third of the hubs.

The H2020 funding, which DIHs use for specific projects and which has a clearly defined end date that can already be anticipated, seems to be a complementary funding sources which allow some specifics actions whereas the DIHs rely on other public funding sources for their structural needs.

In conclusion however, it can be stated that DIHs in general continue to combine various funding instruments for their operations.

Main funding sources	DIHs population
Regional funding	184
National specific innovation funding	177
Horizon 2020	174
Private funding	160
Partner resources	151
European Regional Development Fund	133
National basic research funding	118
Memberships	94
European Social Fund	50
COSME	43

2.1.3 Market sectors

Not surprisingly, many of the DIHs are currently focused on manufacturing as there are a number of national initiatives focusing on industry 4.0³ and DIHs have been an important part of the Digitising European Industry Initiative.⁴ Other sectors such as agriculture and healthcare also require further

³ See for example Industry 4.0 in Germany, Smart Industry in the Netherlands, etc.

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/pillars-digitising-european-industry-initiative>

support as they present some of the less digitized sectors⁵ and are likely to benefit from digital tools that could help with labour-intensive tasks as well as with customer transactions and collaboration among the many connected small players.

Interestingly, education has been mentioned as a sector of interest by about half of the DIHs, indicating the increasing need for skills development. This is also indicated by the large number of DIHs that offer education and skills development services (see table below). Public administration and defence appears to be highlighted by only about one third of the DIHs, despite the comparatively recent emphasis by the Commission on this target client group.

Market Sectors	DIHs Population
Manufacture of machinery and equipment	178
Manufacture of electrical and optical equipment	156
Education	146
Transport, storage and communication	143
Health and social work	133
Manufacture of transport equipment	130
Agriculture, hunting and forestry	128
Other Manufacturing	127
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products	114
Manufacture of food products, beverages and tobacco	114
Manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products	110
Electricity, gas and water supply	109
Construction	106
Manufacture of textiles and textile products	93
Public administration and defence	90
Manufacture of chemicals, chemical products and man-made fibres	89
Manufacture of wood and wood products	87
Other community, social and personal service activities (media, entertainment, etc.)	74

⁵ See Jacques Bughin et al (2016), “Digital Europe: Pushing The Frontier, Capturing The Benefits”, McKinsey report, available [here](#)

Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	72
Wholesale and retail trade	70
Manufacture of leather and leather products	54
Manufacture of pulp, paper and paper products; publishing and printing	53
Financial intermediation	51
Hotels and restaurants	45
Manufacture of coke, refined petroleum products and nuclear fuel	45
Real estate, renting and business activities	39
Fishing	31
Mining and quarrying	28

2.1.4 Services provided

Service Provided	DIHs Population
Ecosystem building, scouting, brokerage, networking	255
Collaborative Research	246
Awareness creation	235
Education and skills development	228
Concept validation and prototyping	226
Testing and validation	221
Incubator/accelerator support	194
Visioning and Strategy Development for Businesses	151
Mentoring	144
Access to Funding and Investor Readiness Services	131
Digital Maturity Assessment	121
Market intelligence	110
Pre-competitive series production	84
Commercial infrastructure	72
Voice of the customer, product consortia	72

The data clearly shows that DIHs are implementing a multi-service portfolio. All three groups of services (technical, ecosystem and business) are offered. Yet, it can be observed that the business related services (such as voice of consumer, digital assessments, access to funding) are slightly less represented. It is here interesting to notice that the Digital maturity assessment is provided by a small minority of DIHs although this specific service can be seen as the starting point for a well conducted Digital Transformation and an open door to pan-DIHs collaboration as the right answer to the need of the companies may not be available in-door. The need for common approaches of this service has already been mentioned by many DIHs. Many networks of DIHs are working on such a common tool. It therefore presents a potential opportunity to extend these efforts to a pan-EU level with a common evaluation method.

Looking at the first 6 services mostly mentioned, one can imagine hypotheses that some DIHs are very much technology oriented in their business model (their added value) while others are more community/ecosystem oriented.

2.1.5 Expertise in Digital technologies

The table below lists the most shared and more available expertise in the DIHs community. It allows us to appreciate already to which extent the technologies identified in the Digital Europe Programme (Supercomputers, AI, cybersecurity) are already covered or not within the community. As it can be seen AI seems to be the more often offered technology (offered by twice as many hubs in comparison to HPC for instance). It also gives an overview of the size of the market for each technologies which could have an impact also on the related business models. This mapping of the available expertise could also help when it comes to bridge the smart specialisation strategies and the DIHs development policies.

Digital Tech. Focus	DIHs Population
Internet of Things (e.g. connected devices, sensors and actuators networks)	241
Artificial Intelligence and cognitive systems	210
Robotics and autonomous systems	196
Simulation and modelling	190
Data mining, big data, database management	188
Cyber physical systems (e.g. embedded systems)	172
Augmented and virtual reality, visualization	169
Interaction technologies (e.g. human-machine Interaction, motion recognition and language technologies)	158
Sensors, actuators, MEMS, NEMS, RF	157
Cloud computing	147
Additive manufacturing (3D printing)	141
Software as a service and service architectures	138
ICT management, logistics and business systems	136
Location based technologies (e.g. GPS, GIS, in-house localization)	130
Cyber security (including biometrics)	123
Micro and nano electronics, smart system integration	114
Advanced or High performance computing	109
Broadband and other communication networks (e.g. 5G)	100
Internet services (e.g. web development & production, design, networking, and e-commerce)	89
Photonics, electronic and optical functional materials	85
Gamification	85
New Media technologies	72
Laser based manufacturing	66
Screens and display technologies	47
Organic and Large Area Electronics (OLAE)	28

2.1.6 Customers

Customers Type	DIHs Population
SMEs (<250 employees)	187
Start-up companies	159
Midcaps (between €2-10 billion turnover)	144
Large companies, multi-nationals	128
Research organisations	93

This last table confirmed what was emerging from previous analysis: SMEs remains the main target of the operating DIHs. This is explainable given the comparative importance of SMEs in the European economy. The need to reach more SMEs - and more traditional SMEs - remain a challenge for all the DIHs. Interestingly however, large companies and mid-caps also present a strong focus for DIHs. This supports conclusions from the XS2I4MS project that large companies should not be underestimated and could also play a significant role within a DIH. The project concluded that *“the role of large firms in digital innovation ecosystems needs careful consideration. These firms could be drivers of digitisation, offering new markets for local and regional SMEs. On the other hand they could also be barriers for digitisation, for example, by having already established their own customised solutions according to standards and requirements of their foreign headquarters.”*⁶

2.2 DIHs Segmentation into 3 coherent groups

2.2.1 Methodology: segmentation by Ascending Hierarchical Classification (AHC) combining several criteria

As mentioned previously, the combination of all the general data given above using the AHC statistical methodology allowed us to identify a segmentation of the 290 European DIH into 3 coherent & homogeneous groups:

- Group 1: gathering 88 DIHs, stronger on their technical expertise and digital services offer than on their network;
- Group 2: gathering 105 DIHs, acting as the average on all the actions expected from DIHs;
- Group 3: gathering 95 DIHs, offering less technical services and/or very specialized services and underfinanced.

⁶ Gijssbers, G. et al (2018), “Deliverable 6.3; Final Report: Cross-case report analysing the results from the Digital Innovation Hub feasibility study projects”, XS2-I4MS report

Figure 1: repartition of DIHs registered in the JRC catalogue of DIH in July 2019 according to 3 homogeneous groups: the MultiTech DIH, the model DIHs and the expert DIHs. F1 & F2 being factorial axes allowing the analysis of the set of qualitative and quantitative data.

2.2.1.1 Group 1: 88 DIHs who play the offer (technologies & services) more than the network and ...

- who offer the most services: 12 on average in this group compared to 9 on average for the general population;
 - who serve the most markets: 13 on average in this group compared to 9 on average for the general population;
 - who drive the most technological expertise, 17 on average in this group compared to an average of 12 in the general population.
- An example of DIH in this category can be found in: [id - 5541 \(VDTC of the Fraunhofer IFF, Germany\)](#)
 - The main funding sources we find in this group are:
 - European Regional Development Fund
 - Regional funding

- The types of DIH organizations in this group are up to 60%: Foundation, Network organisation without formal structure and Private organisation
- The services we find most often are:
 1. Access to Funding and Investor Readiness Services
 2. Digital Maturity Assessment
 3. Incubator/accelerator support
 4. Market intelligence
 5. Mentoring
 6. Visioning and Strategy Development for Businesses
- The 16 most often provided technologies:
 - Internet of Things (e.g. connected devices, sensors and actuators networks)
 - Advanced or High performance computing
 - Augmented and virtual reality, visualization
 - Broadband and other communication networks (e.g. 5G)
 - Cloud computing
 - Cyber security (including biometrics)
 - Data mining, big data, database management
 - ICT management, logistics and business systems
 - Internet of Things (e.g. connected devices, sensors and actuators networks)
 - Interaction technologies (e.g. human-machine Interaction, motion recognition and language technologies)
 - Internet services (e.g. web development, web production, design, networking, and e-commerce)
 - Location based technologies (e.g. GPS, GIS, in-house localization)
 - Micro and nano electronics, smart system integration
 - New Media technologies
 - Screens and display technologies
 - Software as a service and service architectures

2.2.1.2 Group 2: 105 DIHs acting as the average for all the services and technologies provided...

...with the exception of the number of partners which is higher and the number of TRLs which is slightly higher as well in comparison to the other two groups.

- An example of DIH in this category can be found in : [id = 13268 \(Danish Technological Institute, Denmark\)](#)
- The main funding sources we find in this group are:
 - National basic research funding
 - Partners' resources
- The types of DIH organizations in this group are up to 52%:
 - Joint venture
 - (part of) Public organization (part of RTO, or university)

- The services we find most often are:
 - Collaborative Researches
 - Concept validation and prototyping
- The technologies most often provided:
 - Internet of Things (e.g. connected devices, sensors and actuators networks)
 - Artificial Intelligence and cognitive systems
 - Augmented and virtual reality, visualization
 - Interaction technologies (e.g. human-machine Interaction, motion recognition and language technologies)
 - Simulation and modelling
 - Internet of Things (e.g. connected devices, sensors and actuators networks)

2.2.1.3 Group 3: gathering 95 DIHs, offering less technical services but very specialized services and mostly with less funding resources

Without exception, all axes are below average. For example, on the number of technologies expertise provided: 6 on average - compared to 12 for the general population and 16 in Group 1.

- An example of DIH in this category can be found in: [id = 13488 \(CP Lab Newcastle, United Kingdom\)](#)
- The main funding sources we find in this group are:
 - National basic research funding
 - Partner resources
- The types of DIH organizations in this group are up to 36%:
 - (Part of) Private organization
 - Project (formalized end time)
 - Governmental agency
- The technologies that are the least presented in this group seem to be those that are the technologies "stars" of the group 1:
 - Advanced or High performance computing
 - Artificial Intelligence and cognitive systems
 - Augmented and virtual reality, visualization
 - Cyber physical systems (e.g. embedded systems)
 - Cyber security (including biometrics)
 - Data mining, big data, database management
 - Interaction technologies (e.g. human-machine Interaction, motion recognition and language technologies)
 - Internet of Things (e.g. connected devices, sensors and actuators networks)
 - Location based technologies (e.g. GPS, GIS, in-house localization)
 - Micro and nano electronics, smart system integration
 - Sensors, actuators, MEMS, NEMS, RF

2.2.2 Application of this segmentation to specific criteria

As explained before, this segmentation in 3 groups is resulting from a combined analysis of various factors. However, it is also important to check whether this segmentation is operating also when you consider only one of the various criteria of the selection.

2.2.2.1 Technological services

The technology “**Internet of Things (e.g. connected devices, sensors and actuators networks)**” (IoT) which is the expertise that is the most provided within the 290 DIHs, offers a significant example. 241 hubs claim to propose this expertise. However, when all the DIHs of the first group provide it, only half of the DIH in the group 3 (54 out of 95) provided it as shown in the table below. Only 8 DIHs out of the 99 DIHs in group 2 don't provide any expertise in IoT.

Figure 2: number of DIH providing expertise in “Internet of things” in the 3 main DIH groups versus number of DIH not providing expertise in IoT)

2.2.2.2 Size of the DIH

Considering that the group 3 seems to gather very specialized DIHs that are focusing on smaller number of technologies but on cutting edge technologies, shall they be considered as working on “niche” market? Are they constituting smaller structures? It was thus interesting to examine the size of each DIHs. And it appears indeed that the DIHs in the group 3 have globally a smaller number of

employees: 46 of them have less than 10 employees and only 7 of them have more than a hundred employees.

Figure 3: number of employees per DIHs per Group

2.2.3 Customers type

We have also examined if one group is targeting a specific customer type or another. What appears at first glance is that all the DIHS work globally with all kind of companies and that there is no obvious trend of one type of customers being left over.

However, in this global trends, it is important to notice that:

- the group 2 is the group which is globally working with more different type of customers; this is maybe the reason why the group 2 is also the one who works the more with large corporation;
- that SMEs are the most targeted customers audience of all the group of DIHs and represent 64% of the DIHs customers;
- It is also interesting to notice that the group 1 is the one that works more with RTOs as customers in comparison to the other two groups.

2.3 Tentative conclusions to the quantitative approach

This quantitative approach based on the analysis of the structural data provided by DIHs is important as it can help us objectivise the individual feedbacks that the DIHNET team has gathered through the individual interviews of DIHs and DIHs networks. It is also a way to objectivise what is usually hidden behind the words “diversity” or “complexity” and “heterogeneity” used when trying to describe the DIHs landscape. Biodiversity for instance is generally considered a strength and classification is a way to help us better understand the various ecosystem that have emerged. This segmentation should therefore be seen in this light. And it is also a way to help those ecosystems to evolve, adapt thanks to a better understanding of their environment and constraints. This better understanding should be the starting point to build pan-European and pan-DIHs collaborations.

It is interesting to see that the predominant funding sources differ per group. This might be due to a number of reasons – technology focus, breath of services offered as well for instance.

3 Qualitative analysis relying on interviews survey and workshop

If a global picture of the DIHs landscape for each of the EU Members States can already been built from the information included in the catalogue this global picture however requests a more specific analysis to have a clearer perception of the challenges at stake in order to reach an effective European network of comparable DIHs collaborating with each other for a joint benefit.

In order to get this clearer picture, DIHNET partners have decided to worked with three tools:

- One to one Interviews of DIHs and European Stakeholders;
- An online survey circulated within the DIHNET community, to coordinators of network of DIHNET, to clusters association etc.
- An online workshop to share the results of the survey and allow direct exchanges between DIHs.

3.1 One to one Interviews

Interviews aimed to better understand the functioning and the focus of DIHs and DIH networks. The following initiatives were approached:

- Smart4Europe CSA
- SmartAnythingEverywhere IAs:
 - Diatomic
 - FED4SAE
 - SmartEEs
 - Tetramax
- MinaSmart (FR)
- Silicon Europe clusters network
- IP4FVG (IT),
- MIDIH
- BEinCPPS (EU),
- SMITZH (NL)
- Digital.Hub Dortmund logistics
- DIH and network of DIHs having taken part to the online survey and/or to 22/07/2019 workshop:
 - Parsec Hub – Genova – Italy
 - ViDIH – Vilnius – Lithuania
 - Eurecat

3.2 Online surveys & Workshop 22nd July 2019: Exploring business models for DIHs sustainability in Europe

3.2.1 Methodology

For the DIHNET WP5 to go further in details in the identification of segmentation criteria that could be of importance for the design of business models that will enhance Pan-European collaboration and to gather further information to complete the one to one interviews, it has been decided to ask the DIHs for new and updated information addressing the following issues:

- description of their profile & members;
- governance model;
- sources of funding and business models;
- description of activities and services according to the 15 services described within the catalogue;
- description of their uniqueness in terms of expertise (technical, application, services...);
- challenges they face;
- expectations and needs from DIH networks;
- expectations and needs towards Pan-European collaboration;
- availability and willingness to work on specific issues including participation to workshops to define further the framework for DIH networks sustainability (Task 5.3 etc.);
- any other issue deemed appropriate to build on DIHNET action plan.

The survey starts by explaining that DIHNET.EU enables the coordination of European, national and regional initiatives directly supporting the digital transformation and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and aims to create a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs and that this is the reason why we asked them to provide us some information that are quite similar to what they might already have shared to be included in the catalogue but also with some more detailed information. It is also clearly stated that this survey is for the DIHs an opportunity to share their challenges with their pairs and with the European Commission.

The survey has been published on the DIHNET community; to all the community first and then within the community's working group dedicated to business models and sustainability. The survey has also been shared on social media and with DIHs networks that the DIHNET members have identified as key partners.

3.2.2 First results of the survey and discussion during the workshop

Before the workshop that was organised on 22nd July to share the 1st results, 50 people have started to answer to the survey and 11 have finalised it. It is interesting also to mention that people attending the workshop were not necessarily the one that had fully completed the survey yet.

The DIHNET team decided to make the best of those first answers, to share them with the audience and use the online workshop to start the discussion with DIHs. The following sections present the first results of the survey.

In order to provoke discussion and also to gather further information, additional proposals and questions were presented during the workshop, asking participants to vote in polls. Therefore, the following sections will first show the results of the questionnaire, followed by the results of the discussions and polls.

3.2.2.1 What are the services delivered by DIHs in Europe according to the DIHNET survey?

What are the services delivered by DIHs in Europe according to DIHNET survey?

Concerning the services that your DIH is not delivering yet, is it due to

It can be for all those reasons at the same time!

Some DIHs are not expected to deliver all those services but only some of them defined from the beginning of their implementation.

Have you identified other services that you are delivering or would like to deliver in the future?

Testing facilities for micro and small companies, also linking them to the European DIH network (by physically visiting them and their infrastructures)

Digital Maturity Index Assessment (Digital Maturity Index) for a dedicated Observatory

Services delivered by DIHs in Europe

- ▶ 4 services are mainly provided by DIHs
 - ▶ Awareness creation
 - ▶ Ecosystem building, scouting, brokerage, networking
 - ▶ Incubator, acceleration support
 - ▶ Education and skill development

- ▶ 3 services are rather lacking
 - ▶ Voice of the customer
 - ▶ Market intelligence
 - ▶ Pre competitive series production

Services delivered by DIHs in Europe

1st SUGGESTION TO BE DISCUSSED

- ▶ The Pan-European collaboration should be focused on supporting the non developed services.
- ▶ Pan-European collaboration could be dedicated to provide and share information and actions to support DIHs for the definition of their support strategy to their members.
- ▶ The objective would be to support DIHs members to be ahead of competition, to work on common representation towards the EC, common goal/strategy setting, EU market assessment, mapping of activities to allow for less repetition & competition.

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3.2.2.1.1 Results from the Webinar regarding services and collaboration

Three questions have been asked to participants during the workshop regarding services.

1. Do you think Pan-European collaboration should first focus on supporting the less developed services in Europe?

What has emerged from the discussion is that it is no use to focus on the less developed services because they can be considered as low priority. What is at stake for DIHs at the moment is to provide their local ecosystem (be it regional or national) with services that will be the more appropriate to answer Companies' needs.

They have a societal and economical mission that is to build a strong and sustainable services offer for their members. Their challenge is also to have their government acknowledging their role vis-à-vis this local ecosystem and its economic vitality.

2. Do you think Pan-European collaboration could be dedicated to share best practises to support DIHs in their services strategy?

The DIHs attending the workshop were unanimously expecting some exchange of best practices in order to learn from each other and in order to be able to focus on their local functions to answers their members' needs. In their comments however they highlighted that

exchanges of best practices should not be the only added-value of pan-European collaboration that should go far further in building the DIHs community.

3. What should be the core aims of a Pan-European collaboration?

Do you think pan-European collaboration should look for:

It is interesting to notice that, despite their willingness to develop their own market and provide their members with the best services possible, DIHs are also quite aware of the need to avoid too many replications and do agree on the principle of a collaborative approach. However, the implementation of this approach remains a challenge.

What is your priority geographical reach?

Priority geographical reach

2nd SUGGESTION TO BE DISCUSSED

- ▶ DIHs have rather a regional and national focus.
- ▶ The Pan-European collaboration could help them to achieve an European reach, but also to develop an International reach through DIHs collaborations.

The question raised to the people attending the workshop was the ability of Pan-European collaboration to help DIHs to achieve European and International reach. The answer was unanimous again. DIHs are expecting Pan-European collaboration to help them reach a wider ecosystem and help their members find new opportunities beyond their local ecosystem.

Do you think pan-European collaboration could help DIHs to achieve European & international reach?

3.2.2.3 DIHs' governance model

What kind of entity is your DIH ?

<input type="radio"/> No new structure but a consortium agreement between partners	5	45%
<input type="radio"/> A legally formalised new entity. Please explain below	2	18%
<input type="radio"/> Evolution from a pre-existing structure. See following question	0	0%
<input type="radio"/> New structure with underlying consortium agreement.	0	0%
<input type="radio"/> Part of a pre-existing organisation. Please explain below	4	36%
<input type="radio"/> A project based organisation. Please explain below	0	0%
<input type="radio"/> Privately owned initiative . Please explain below	0	0%
<input type="radio"/> Other	0	0%

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What kind of partners are actively and formally participating in your DIH?

There are several PIDs in Italy, each of them have several agreement with local, regional and national partners; therefore there are some more general national agreements (Umbrella agreements) with some National RTOs, for example the Italian CNR or the ENEA which are two of the most important research agencies in Italy."

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DIHs legal entities

3rd SUGGESTION TO BE DISCUSSED

- ▶ At this stage, no specific type of entity for DIHs
- ▶ Would it make sense to define a specific DIHs entity to reinforce collaborations and join activities?

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The question raised during the webinar is whether working on a common European formal framework to build a DIH upon could be of any help to reinforce collaboration between DIHs.

This is a very challenging question indeed. Some people consider a common framework as a way to structure the ecosystem and to work on the same legal basis. It could be a way to help new DIHs to build their activity, a kind of guidelines on how to start a DIH.

Others consider that reaching a consensus on a common framework would be a very time consuming aim that would not necessary bring any benefit. The risk seems to be increasing complexity and workload in an already complex and busy situation with a huge variety of different DIHs starting their activities and finding out how to collaborate better with their alter ego.

Would it make sense to define a specific DIHs entity to reinforce collaborations and join activities?

3.2.2.4 DIHs and Smart specialisation

How is your DIH connected to the regional Smart Specialization Strategy ?

Are you currently collaborating with other DIHs?

- On specific technologies:**
- Artificial Intelligence
 - Robotics & Automation
 - Health
 - Bio-materials for construction
 - Packaging
 - IOT/CPS/Big data

What are the main challenges faced by your organization in setting-up those collaborations?

Where do you see the most added value in collaborating with other DIHs?

o Sharing infrastructure (labs, testing infra, etc)	7	64%
o Accessing technology expertise not available in-house	9	82%
o Accessing sector/domain expertise not available in-house	9	82%
o Identifying best practices	9	82%
o Identifying (common) challenges among companies	3	27%
o Working in common research projects (EU or national)	9	82%
Other	0	0%

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Most added value in collaborating with other DIHs

4th SUGGESTION TO BE DISCUSSED

- ▶ The interest for Pan-European collaboration relies on accessing to additional technology, competencies, identifying best practices, working on common projects
- ▶ Do you consider that the definition of a business models for Pan-European DIHs should address in priority the following aims:
 - perform joint research on DIHs members needs and challenges (SMEs levels) to define collectively European Actions to be undertaken;
 - engage working groups for best practices sharing at DIHs levels
 - benefit for a « label » as member of a group/community
 - benefit for specific services supporting DIHs collaboration.

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Taking into account the results of the survey emphasising the importance to access technologies and competences not available in house, to exchange best practices and to work on common research projects, people attending the workshop were asked to prioritise the main tasks business models for pan-European collaboration between DIH should focus on.

3.2.2.6 Results from the Webinar on business models and collaboration

Do you consider that the definition of a business models for Pan-European DIHs should address in priority the following aims:

It is important here to notice that the participation to a community to benefit from a kind of “quality label” seems quite a demonetized idea that does not raise a lot of enthusiasm. The added-value of joining a community has to be find elsewhere and especially in sharing best practices and knowledge to foster collaboration.

3.2.2.7 *Expectations towards the European Commission to strengthen Pan-European collaboration between DIHs*

What could be the inputs from the European Commission to strengthen those collaborations ?

- ▶ Provide funding/incentives for collaboration activities (cf EEN network)
- ▶ Mentoring: dedicated help for new DIHs to catch up with developed ones
- ▶ A common platform for DIH to communicate, to identify possible common challenges and opportunities and to organise brokerage events. Provide a shared searchable database for technologies & competences.
- ▶ Networking: support for networking between DIHs
- ▶ Sectorial watch: niche reports on different industry sectors
- ▶ Collaborating with regional authorities to reduce the fragmentation of the offer by identifying and/or promoting a rationalisation of the current DIHs landscape.

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What would be your recommendations to support pan-European collaboration between DIHs at European level?

o Funding interregional SME experiments (please elaborate)	5	56%
o Supporting visits to DIHs in other regions/countries (please elaborate)	5	56%
o Facilitate company visits (please elaborate)	5	56%
o Facilitate exchange of services between DIHs	6	67%
o Joined strategy development (please elaborate)	4	44%
o Mentoring programme for new DIHs and more mature DIHs (please elaborate)	7	78%
o Networking and brokerage schemes (please elaborate)	6	67%

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3.3 Conclusion from the survey and webinar

The discussion between DIHs has started during this first DIHNET workshop designed to explore business models and DIHs sustainability in Europe. Attendees have been invited to join the DIHNET community and to complete the survey if it was not already done. It has been emphasized that the survey would remain open for a few weeks in order to reach more DIHs and to gather more answers and build an even stronger analysis.

However, a few conclusive remarks can be done already:

- There is a strong interest for Pan-European collaboration but a still too vague idea of what that would really mean.
- The interest of DIHs for a joint approach of a Pan-European collaborations between DIHs can be considered as the first conclusion of the survey and the workshop. Most of them have a strong local & national ecosystem but are expecting some guidelines or common framework to share best practices, technologies and skills with other DIHs. However, it seems that it is too early for most of the DIHs involved in the survey and the workshop to identify the services and technologies they would need to import or be ready to export. The need for time to build a strong and useful offer at the local level comes first.
- Many DIHs are quite young structures although most of them are an emanation or an evolution from pre-existing structures. The priority for them at the moment seems more to consolidate a local and technological positioning than to start building Pan-European collaborations beyond their current participation to European research projects.

4 DIHNET conceptual analysis business model considerations from various viewpoints

Based on the experience of the DIHNET team with DIHs and the information gathered from the activities described above, the following section will provide a conceptual discussion on the topic of business models from the perspective of EU collaboration.

DIHs are seen as an appropriate tool to support industry in the digital transition and provide companies, and especially SMEs, with a one-stop shop where they can “access to technology-testing, financing advice, market intelligence and networking opportunities.”⁷ A key feature of the DIHs is indeed that they offer a combination of technology, business and ecosystem services. Digital Innovation Hubs have steadily increased during the last 5 years, supported by European and national strategies and programs. Next to these DIHs, we also observe that different networks on regional level as well in thematic networks on national and EU level (eg Smart Agri Hubs, RODIN network of robotics DIHs, Photonics and we can expect centres of excellence in AI, etc) are emerging. These are often initiatives in addition, already existing networks on national platforms, clusters, sectorial organizations and European networks such as Idealist, EEN, etc. As a result, **DIHs operate in a complex**, multi-layered ecosystem that it still difficult to picture, structure and coordinate. This is an important development because the objectives, the services and the **business models for each of these levels differ** in some aspects and overlap in others.⁸

The following analysis aims to structure the thinking regarding business models while acknowledging the complexity of the DIH landscape at present. For this it is crucial to create an overview of the different ‘animals’ active in Europe and attempt to see at what level (local, regional, national, EU, international) they operate. The discussion starts with an introduction of the different entities in the EU DIH ecosystem and what services they would be interested in offering. Next to the possible services offered at different levels, it is also crucial to analyse the possible funding sources available to these animals, including private and public funding. The discussion ends with some preliminary conclusions.

4.1 Who offers what services at which level⁹

As mentioned above, different initiatives are currently operating simultaneously in Europe. The following initiatives can be distinguished¹⁰ (see Figure below):

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-innovation-hubs>

⁸ See D6.1: Inception Report, DIHNET.EU report (2019), as well as K. Karanikolova, M. Butter, G. Gijbsbers, A. Goetheer (forthcoming), “Digital Innovation Hubs and their position in the European, national and regional innovation ecosystem”, in Denise Feldner (ed.), Chapter in: ‘Redesigning Organizations - Concepts for the Connected Society’, Springer Nature Switzerland

⁹ This section is the result of analysis within the DIHNET framework as well as previous projects such as EU-GREAT!, XS2I4MS, SmartEEss and a number of individual DIH training provided by TNO in Basque country, Galicia, Trondheim, internal training on PPP business models, etc.

¹⁰ See K. Karanikolova, M. Butter, G. Gijbsbers, A. Goetheer (forthcoming), “Digital Innovation Hubs and their position in the European, national and regional innovation ecosystem”, in Denise Feldner (ed.), Chapter in: ‘Redesigning Organizations - Concepts for the Connected Society’, Springer Nature Switzerland as well as Kristina Karanikolova, Maurits Butter, Govert Gijbsbers (2019), “Development of Digital Innovation Hubs | Final report”, TNO 2019 R10324

Figure 1: Different animals and their functions (Maurits Butter, 2019, as part of the work on DIHNET)

- Individual DIHs:** Individual DIHs are usually consortia of partners that form a dedicated entity to address a number of services and activities connected to technology, business and ecosystem support. DIHs tend to combine tech with business and ecosystem related services as they aim to address a wide range of different needs of the regional ecosystem.¹¹ They support SMEs not only with technology knowledge but also with adoption of innovations and respective (operational, value chain, financial) challenges. This also reflects the Commission's idea that DIHs should support companies with 'testing before investing' – a term which implies more than just technological test but also potential considerations for return on investment, etc

Most of the DIHs appear to offer about 10 services or more (10 of the services are offered by more than 55% of the DIH participating in the DIHNET survey described above). This supports the previous assumptions that DIHs need to combine a wide service portfolio to be able to respond to the needs of the ecosystem and also offer the found functionalities (test before invest, ecosystem building and networks, skills and training and support with investments) identified by the EC.

DIHs are often focused on their regional ecosystems as they often are aiming to approach the corporates in a relatively close distance. Therefore, the services portfolio of the individual DIHs are likely to reflect the regional needs. This means that some DIHs might be focused on offering high-tech solutions, while others might need to raise awareness and understanding of digital opportunities (such as the more business and ecosystem group identified by the segmentation). More likely, a combination of the two would be present. This is also showcased by the segmentation analysis conducted on the catalogue. Three typologies of

¹¹ See K. Karanikolova, M. Butter, G. Gijbbers, A. Goetheer (forthcoming), "Digital Innovation Hubs and their position in the European, national and regional innovation ecosystem", in Denise Feldner (ed.), Chapter in: 'Redesigning Organizations - Concepts for the Connected Society'

DIHs are found with some of them showcasing more technology oriented focus (see chapter 2).

Individual DIHs could be seen as focusing more on one technology area and/or sector as it is difficult for one organization (even if it is a consortium) to address the whole spectrum of technologies and sectors). Usually this expertise on the technology domain would be based on the participating Competence Centres who often take the lead in providing technology oriented services such as prototyping and conducting I R&D projects. The sector knowledge could be embedded in the CC but could also be provided by the different cluster or industry organizations that connect the DIH to industry and could form part of the DIH consortium. Chambers of Commerce or authorities specifically dedicated to SMEs can provide access to the DIH main audience – the companies in their region. As individual DIHs are often focused on the regional community and SMEs, they are also often relying on (some) regional funding, at least at the start of their operations.

- **Regional networks of DIHs¹²** – currently, one can notice that also clustering of DIHs into regional networks is explored in different parts of Europe. This could be a self-organization among the DIHs or it could be led by regional or event national authority or programme depending on the local situation. There are many reasons for such coordination, from ensuring a one window-shop for companies, to running more efficiently the DIHs in a single region, to reducing the burden on individual DIHs by pooling resources and ensuring economies of scale for some of the services. In such networks, could offer support to individual DIHs (such as peer learning) or some services could be ‘outsourced’ to the DIH network (eg. monitoring of existing funding mechanisms on EU and national level) while the individual hubs act as nodes with specific expertise. Regional networks are therefore often cross-domain/technology, having a broad understanding of innovation issues and being able to re-direct the question to the relevant DIH node.

The basic reasoning is that some of the activities of the different hubs could be pooled together to benefit from economies of scale. For instance, regional DIH networks could take charge of the ecosystem related services, raising awareness of the benefits of digitization and the specific technologies and solutions offered by the individual DIHs. Similarly, some of the business related services such as accelerator and access to finance support are likely to be relevant for various sectors and technologies and can be organized by a central entity. Skills and education is another field, where some modules can be offered by a regional DIH network, with the different DIH nodes offering specialized expertise. Also peer learning on how to organize and offer skills development as well as company-student collaborations could be explored. Such networks would often have a regional authority as a leading or coordinating entity. This could be a useful link especially as it could enable the DIHs networks to connect to the specialization strategies of the regions, as well as coordinate pan-EU collaboration as that is one of the goals of regions.

¹² See also Butter, M., & Karanikolova, K. (2018), “Support to development of a Basque digital innovation Hub”, TNO report, Project reference code: 931101

- EU hubs** – the current Digital Europe Program sees DIHs as a central tool to support companies in adopting new technologies. European Hubs will probably be nominated of the MS, and should be representing more or less each region in Europe. Recent survey from the JRC concluded that currently most DIHs target AI as an enabling technology and the other 3 techs which are in the focus of the DEP are indicated as priorities to a much lesser extent by DIHs.¹³ Current understanding appears to be that EU DIHs can be both regional DIH networks or individual DIHs. In any case, there will also be other brand of hubs that also co-exist with the other hubs. E-DIHs are expected receive co-funding from regions and national authorities to run and develop the hub and from the EC to facilitate the pan-EU collaboration with other hubs. Still funding in H2020 and other EU and regional funding is not precluded for the rest DIHs (not branded as European). It remains to be seen how the funding priorities will be structured as well as how the different hubs will cooperate.
- Pan-European (thematic) DIH networks:** Currently we can also observe that there are initiatives aiming to develop networks of DIHs with similar thematic focus. Examples include the IAs, also coordinated by CSAs and individually started networks and PPPs. ... Sustainable business models for such networks still need to be developed and tested and that is the aim of many of the initiatives currently running. It is important to note that the target stakeholder for these networks is not the SMEs (these are addressed indirectly) but rather the DIHs/DIH regional networks. A first overview of the possible services that such networks can offer with added value for their members is shown in the figure on the right.

Figure 2: pan-EU network activities (M. Butter, 2019)

4.2 Possible funding sources at the different levels

Next to the services offering adding value and the target group, an important part of the business model is the financing of DIHs. This should include an analysis of the funding options, including the possible income from the activities of the hubs as well as the use of public and private funding. The following sections outline this discussion.

¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=60617, Gabriel Rissola, “Putting DIHs into Regional Context: a EU Survey” Digital Innovation Hubs Working Group's Sixth Meeting Brussels, 1 st July 2019

4.2.1 Public funding and in-kind contributions usually needed to set up and initiate the DIH, followed by (expected) decrease of public funding

Digital Innovations Hubs aim to “help ensure that every company, small or large, high-tech or not, can grasp the digital opportunities”.¹⁴ As with any other public-private partnership, the development of a DIH follows different stages, each requiring different funding instruments.

Previous research indicates¹⁵ that the preparation and initiation stages of a DIH can be time and cost intensive. Resources are needed to study the demand, form a consortium, test the feasibility and maybe even acquire some infrastructure. Often, a lot of effort and in-kind contributions are provided by the partners and due to both high risk and more public nature of activities, private funding in this period is challenging. On the other hand, public funding is only available when the DIHs address a specific market failure, and therefore, the state aid rules need to be observed. When the tool to address this market failure is a DIH, one can expect that regional/national/EU funds would be dedicated at the start. However, as the market failure (starts) being addressed, one can expect a decrease in the public funding over time. At the same time, as the DIHs start operating, they would probably generate income from the services offered or from membership schemes.¹⁶ **Public funding (at least a basic level) would often still be needed throughout the existence of the DIH, but can be expected to decrease (but not disappear).**

This does not however mean that **private funding** is not used or common. A study in the Netherlands in 2018 showed that all 10 of the studied field-labs (out of the then 32 existing such entities) have used private funding in their operations (see figure below).¹⁷ Private partners are willing to participate and support

Field labs	Sources of funding					
	Regional	Knowledge institutes	TKI	National	European	Private
Region of Smart Factories	x			x	x	x
Campione	x				x	x
Fresh Teq	x	x			x	x
The Garden	x	x		x	x	x
Smart Connected Supplier Network	x		x	x		x
Flexible Manufacturing	x	x	x		x	x
Smart Dairy Farming		x	x			x
Smart Bending Factory	x				x	x
Multimateriaal 3D printing	x				x	x
Ultra-Personalized Products and Services		x	x			x

Figure 3: Field labs and their funding sources (source: Claire Stolwijk, Matthijs Punter (2018), ‘Going Digital Smart Industry Field labs in the Netherlands’)

¹⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-innovation-hubs>

¹⁵ XS2I4MS Mentoring Programme and EU-GREAT! projects all discuss the mix of public/private funding needed. Also see Marcel de Heide and Maurits Butter (2016), “Deliverable 5.3 Report assessment match/mismatch and issues with combined funding”,

¹⁶ Maurits Butter and Monique Sonnemans (2017), “Financing and Innovation Hub”, Mentoring Material and webinar given as part of the XS2I4MS project. See also Butter, M., & Karanikolova, K. (2018), “Support to development of a Basque digital innovation Hub”, TNO report, Project reference code: 931101;

Butter, M., Karanikolova, K., Gijsbers, G. (2019), “Development of Digital Innovation Hubs | Final report”, report for the development of a DIH in Trondheim, TNO 2019 R10324;

Karanikolova, K. Butter, M. (2019), “Development of Digital Innovation Hubs”, report for GAIN,

¹⁷ Claire Stolwijk, Matthijs Punter (2018), ‘Going Digital Smart Industry Field labs in the Netherlands’, TNO 2018 R10453, available at: <https://www.smartindustry.nl/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/TNO-2018-R10453-OECD-report-Going-Digital-Smart-Industry-field-labs-final-May-31-2018-final.pdf>

DIHs for various reasons – from trying to address common challenges, to attempting to make the ecosystem more competitive. The level of private funding can vary significantly among different DIHs, but previous research indicates that public fund commitments can also provide incentives for private parties to join.¹⁸ In conclusion, it can be said that individual DIHs often need to match a number of funding sources for their operation.

4.2.2 Different funding sources and their applicability to the different levels in the DIH landscape¹⁹

4.2.2.1 Public funding²⁰

- **EU funding** – in the current funding period, EU funding with regard to DIHs was mainly targeting exploring and the establishment of DIHs (see I4MS) as well as mapping of existing initiatives (the DIH Catalogue). The future DEP programme would provide financing to establish a pan-EU collaboration among hubs and networks, focusing also on capacities as well as requiring matching national/regional investments. EU funding is usually project based or provided via grants and co-funding (large scale RDI projects). Support for the individual SMEs can be found via instruments such as the experiments with the IA (cascade funding) and DIHs can be intermediaries in the organization of experiments. H2020 funding is usually cited as a planned income for DIHs, but it should be noted that it focuses on excellence of R&D and innovative projects. Therefore, not all SMEs could be beneficiaries of cascade funding- some might not be interested in experiments. The DEP programme and other complementary plans (Invest EU) are currently discussed on EU level to also address this issue.
- **National funding** – mostly in infrastructure and interest to dedicate funds to support general economic prosperity Regional and national funds are also expected to contribute to the DEP co-funding scheme. As described by the EC, “Member States and regions should invest in the creation or reinforcement of Digital Innovation Hubs that support their national/regional digitalisation strategy.”²¹
- **Regional funding:** regions are often willing to support DIHs as the individual DIHs are focussed on supporting the regional development and SMEs. Regions might find it even more attractive to support regional DIH networks and leverage on their combined outreach. Also the fact that regional funding is not that focused on excellence of research, regional authorities might support ecosystem development, skills development related activities. Innovation vouchers could be used to also attract SMEs. Regions also have access to ERDF funds and therefore dedicate funds to their determined specialization strategies. As regions differ, one can expect that some can dedicate more money through ERDF while others less. Also based on the regional development, DIHs might not be a priority for funding, therefore creating a barrier for some DIHs.

¹⁸ Claire Stolwijk, Marcel de Heide, Tom van der Horst (2017), ‘Financing Field Labs’, TNO 2017 R10964, available at: <https://www.kansenvoorwest2.nl/files/tno-financieringvanfieldlabs.pdf>

¹⁹ XS2I4MS and EU-GREAT! projects discuss the mix of public/private funding needed. Also see Marcel de Heide and Maurits Butter (2016), “Deliverable 5.3 Report assessment match/mismatch and issues with combined funding”,

²⁰ See I4MS Mentoring programme information, available here: <https://i4ms.eu/mentoring-programme/access-to-finance/funding-sources>

²¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-innovation-hubs>

- **In-kind contributions** from the competence centres and RTOs participating in the DIHs and the networks are frequent as reaching out the companies and supporting them is also part of their responsibilities. Similar can be the situation for regional development agencies and training institutes. These in-kind contributions should not be underestimated and could actually provide a significant portion of the operating budget of the hub.

4.2.2.2 *Private investments*

Private investments in DIHs and regional DIH networks can be seen as debt and equity financing or via partners in the hub. The latter is seen for instance in the Netherlands where the field-labs have also received private funding from companies participating as partners in the field-labs. Their rationale is that together in the field-lab they can work on a common challenge.

For debt financing, as mentioned previously loans are not that easy to secure, especially at the start as the risk for the debt provider are high on either the initiative would be successful and on securing their investment with any collateral.

Equity financing by VC and accelerators are possible but still difficult as they usually look for high growth, high profitability investments with fast and high ROI. And as many DIHs are non-for profit, the interest of private investors in them is not that high. Still, such entities can be attracted as partners in the DIH, regional networks where they can find a pool of possible clients.

4.2.2.3 *Income from services*

Some DIHs and DIH networks would be able to charge for their services. (Renting or paid for use) access to infrastructure might be in demand, especially for early adopters who need access to specialized or technology but for shorter periods or ad hoc access to testing facilities. Yet, the regional situation would determine the extent to which private parties can afford such services. difficult for them to pay for these services. While many companies would be interested in the ecosystem services, few would be willing to pay for them.²² In this case a membership model might work better to collect small fees for general ecosystem and awareness service (but usually in their region of interest). The **membership model**, with different tiers granting access to different services, is in general a good option for DIHs which need to have basic funding, to sustain their operations. This can also support the DIHs and the regional DIH networks in creating a funnel to attract further clients. Still, it is likely that also public funding would be needed to cover the difference between the income from services and the expenses of the hub more connected to societal services like demonstrations and ecosystem learning.

In case there is a network of DIHs, a model for distribution of resources should be established. Depending on the structure of the network (whether the network presents a single window to the customer and manages the project or it only aims to coordinate some activities such as representation of the interests and inter-regional cooperation), different models of funding can be established – eg. the network organization distributing the public funds, the individual nodes contributing a percentage to run the overall network, or a regional agency fulfilling the network function completely.

Yet, in discussions with DIHs and networks, many note that income and funding are a key challenge. In many cases that is because some of the services are not per se commercial but targeting a more

²² See XS214MS webinar on “Access to Finance”, available here: <https://i4ms.eu/mentoring-programme/access-to-finance/income>

common development aim (ecosystem building) and even because in some cases companies find it difficult to pay for services.

4.2.2.4 *Pan-EU collaboration and income*²³

Income from services is especially interesting and complex in the pan-EU collaboration scheme. Business models are needed to convince a DIH or a DIH network as to why they need to send their customer to a different entity outside of their scope and how they are supposed to manage that relationship. One possibility is to plan a percentage of the payment by the client as a project management fee which the DIH in the clients' region receives for finding the right partner hub and for assisting with the customer relation. The hub (or network) in another region providing the bulk of the services can then receive also the bulk of the payment. Still, how to resolve the different payment rates, find other business models and facilitate the collaboration remains a challenge outside of ad-hoc European projects (H2020, etc).

Memberships are particularly interesting mechanism when we discuss the development of networks on EU level and their added value. Looking at the possible services that can be offered by pan-EU networks, many target the group (rather than a one-on-one service for a single DIH), making the membership model even more relevant. Some membership income can also be received from industrial associations if for instance the pan-EU network works on standards or strategic agendas for these associations. Market analysis research can be seen as another source of income with some of the insights being made available for all, while the whole report only distributed to 'gold members' or upon further payment for instance. Still, many of the continuous services of such a network would need to be supported by probably a mix of public funding and some kind of a membership approach.

Yet, one should consider that some of these stakeholders (eg associations or DIHs themselves) are struggling financially as well and might find it difficult for dedicate funds for memberships.

4.3 Concluding: business models are crucial but difficult both for individual DIHs and for pan-EU collaboration

The different levels of DIHs require different business models as they can add different value to different audience. It is key to establish what the added value of each of the possible structures (DIH, regional DIH network, pan EU collaboration network) is.

- DIHs are still very much focused on their own development. Some DIHs are of course more advanced than others, but as they are comparatively new entities, DIHs are focusing on establishing their position and added value in their own outreach. Therefore, for them to actively engage in collaboration, it needs to be clear what the added value for each of the partners would be. There appears to be demand for good practices sharing, possible cross-use of facilities and strategic orientation (agenda setting). But outlining how this mechanism will exactly work (including resources flow and responsibilities) requires some further exploration.
- Individual DIHs offer many of the identified 14 services described in the JRC Catalogue. Some of these are addressed by the majority of the hubs – eg awareness creation, ecosystem

²³ See Butter, M., & Karanikolova, K. (2018), "Support to development of a Basque digital innovation Hub", TNO report, Project reference code: 931101 and M.Butter et al (2019), "Business Models for pan-EU networks", presentation given at the RODIN summer camp in October 2019, in Leiden

development, etc. Some of these activities are addressing a market failure and have a societal mission, meaning that some of these services might need to be publicly funded.

- Funding differs depending on the aim/objective of the initiative in combination with the aims of the funding source. Public funding might be needed on a continuous basis but should not be the only option and other alternatives need to also be explored to prepare the hubs for future. For this, finding their value added where they can achieve impacts is crucial.

5 Conclusions

Based on the interviews and the analysis, several inputs can be highlighted and work hypothesis can be made that will be further explored during the DIHNET project and within a future workshop that will be organised in 2020 to set-up the foundation of Pan-European collaboration.

5.1 The huge diversity in the DIHs community does not mean a huge and too complicated diversity in the potential business models

5.1.1 Impact of the structuration of DIH on their business models

5.1.1.1 *Funding sources and organisational form*

The diversity of the DIHs in Europe is significant and categorization/ segmentation offers clear indication of this. Interestingly, it appears that the funding sources predominantly used vary among the three identified clusters of DIHs. However, the organizational form and the sectors addressed does not seem to affect the business models of the DIHs more than its impact on the contractualisation rules.

5.1.1.2 *Customers types*

More probably, the potential clients addressed by DIHs activities may have an impact on the business models in their ability and willingness to pay for the provided services. Interestingly however, public administrations are less often seen as a target for DIHs despite the emphasis put on this client group by the EC. Therefore, it will be interesting for the future to study what particular activities DIHs offer to public authorities, how this affects their business model and whether issues such as state aid and public procurement procedures affect their offering towards public bodies.

5.1.1.3 *Constitution of the network*

The services offered by the DIHs and the DIH networks differ. This distinction is very logical when one considered the direct target group of each entity. While DIH networks aim to support companies and can for example help them find the right partner, networks also perform many activities related to coordination, finding synergies, supporting individual partners and facilitating collaborations. Consequently, the business models for these entities will differ. It will be interesting to explore in the future whether differences exist among networks strongly supported by public (regional or national) authorities and those that are more independently driven and whether there are differences in the added value.

Moreover, the aim of a DIH being to fill the gap to strengthen the ecosystem and not to create new competition, the definition of each DIH business model has to take into account the business models of its partners in order to not duplicate the services offers.

In this sense, collaboration and specialization within and outside regions is all the more important to consider to create emulation and complementarity instead of replication or competition.

5.1.1.4 *Maturity*

The development and implementation of a sustainable business models for the DIHs still appear to be challenging. Most of DIHs are faced with the reality and constraints of designing a set of services that will allow them to address a wide and diverse clients target, combining a number of technologies to meet local needs and matching funding sources. As some of them already mentioned it, DIHs may also

need further support for their own development and for the fine tuning of business models that will allow them go a step further in Pan-European collaboration.

DIHs as well as DIH networks are still very much developing. Many of the networks still provide support for further business models and services development to the individual DIHs. This signifies that the DIHs are still to be treated as more or less start-ups which require different support. The support demanded can vary – from scanning and participation in EU calls to support with expanding the service portfolio or learning from peers.

5.1.2 Potential business models to be explored further

However, whatever the size of the DIHs or of the DIHs networks, the business models sustaining their activities will vary in proportion for one to another but they will follow some global trends. The potential contributors being always the same stakeholders – mainly DIHs partners, customers or founders – the diversity of business models will depend of strategic choices according to who is the most interested to pay for.

For example, the most provided services awareness creation and ecosystem building can be built following a few standard business models:

- membership fee
- payment for services
- possibilities to advertise success or services (requires a strong existing brand of the DIH networks to ensure wide public)
- Concerning the technical services, the same reasoning can be made. Here renting of infrastructures, payment per use, add-on business models to get further functionality of a platform or more detailed support, beta testing equipment, and even advertising technologies as a demonstration facility could be options for business models. The choice will depend on the available technological infrastructure and the demand.

Looking at the segmentation of the individual DIHs and especially their funding mechanisms, one can see that for some regional funding is very important but that memberships and private investments are also utilized by some. This raises the hypothesis that different business models can be distinguished: For instance, DIHs with a perceived strategic regional importance (due to lack of other available support or that DIHs are seen as strategic for future development) might be seen as strategic to align activities, therefore offering a broad services and technology portfolio and are probably more heavily supported by regional funding. Different roles – as leading or supporting existing initiatives could be envisioned based on what is already available in the region. In any case, for such entities, it is likely that reaching to SMEs is key.

For those more commercially active entities that have implemented membership model for (at least some) activities or have attracted private funding, one can imagine that the focus would be on the goals of the private investors and members – searching what is the most added value for this particular group. Outreach to other SMEs is likely to still be important but to a lesser extent. Further study and potential examples are needed to study these hypothesis as part of the upcoming workshops and webinars part of the WP5.

5.2 Pan-European cooperation is a positive perspective but still need some time and incentives to be put in practice

5.2.1 The expected benefits of collaboration among DIHs...

The benefits of collaboration among DIHs are well acknowledged in theory. Yet, one can observe that collaboration even on national level among existing network initiatives (in competence centres, centres of innovation, DIHs, KETs, etc) is still challenging.

Possibilities to find complementary expertise among EU partners is attractive and many partners are using existing tools and previous relationships to establish a connection with relevant partners. Yet, possibilities to further map the expertise and capacities of DIHs might be needed with the continuously increasing number of hubs and other ecosystem players.

Collaborations to explore synergies and possible partnerships (eg with other DIHs in the same country or on EU level) is seen as beneficial.

5.2.2 ...still to be concretely implemented

However, the need for Pan-European collaboration vary greatly depending of the size and the strength of the DIHs' ecosystem. Some DIHs with wide, rich and strong local ecosystems do not always have the same expectations and needs than smaller ecosystems or very specialised ones that really see the added value of widening their reach and get to know new partners.

The perceived benefits of common approaches and dissemination of lessons learned that can be translated to other organizations are only partially met (and sometimes on a limited basis). Most of the DIHs are still in their starting phase when external support is welcome. This is especially the case for the development of their business models and of their services portfolio. Many DIHs expressed their interest for good practices and peer-learning. Different ideas such as supporting common approaches, templates, sharing or making use of each other's demonstrators was also mentioned as an opportunity for EU collaboration.

Beyond the need for business models that could foster Pan-European cooperation, many DIHs highlighted the interest of European projects to build-up the DIHs community and to build-up the trust among partners. They were confident in the fact that cooperation will come logically as the DIHs will get to know each other better.

Exploring possible future business models for such collaboration (including not only funding but also discussions on what exactly can be provided, to which entities, and what mechanisms could be used) requires more exploration and will be further looked at as part of WP5.